

[Print](#)**Teacher Education through Urdu Medium Is a Need of the Day**

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Abstract

The Urdu is one of the major Modern Indian Languages, which is widely spoken in India. It is almost second largely spoken language in many states. At the same time, the readers and teachers of this language are in minority. Teaching of Urdu as a language may require some efforts, but teaching of all subjects in Urdu medium requires more creativity and labour of teachers. This means that training of teachers to teach in this medium needs a careful design of the programme, which should be tailor made for the requirement of the beneficiaries. That is why, there are issues and problems pertaining to academic, administrative and evaluation aspects of the teacher education programmes. The training of different types of teachers i.e. pre-service or in-service have their own priorities and issues to be addressed. The campus mode or distance mode programmes require their own infrastructure and facilities. The short term or long duration programmes have its own need and implications. This article looks into different problems encountered during teacher education through Urdu medium.

Introduction

Urdu is one of the important modern Indian languages, which is widely spoken and understood across the nation. The speakers of Urdu are present in minority all over India, but their presence cannot be neglected. The progress of the nation in a globalised society is possible only with the help of inclusion of backward groups like Urdu community. Teachers play a key role in upliftment of this group, and as per Kothari Commission (1964-66), they shape the destiny of nation in four walls of our classroom. This is why, the national policy of education 1986, emphasised on teachers as it said that the socio-cultural ethos of a society is reflected by the status of teachers. Therefore, training of teachers whether pre-service or in-service, campus or non-campus, short term or long term, Urdu or non-Urdu is of